

NOVEL METHODS OF ASSESSING INTER-PLY PROPERTIES OF TOUGHENED PREPREGS IN APPLICATION TO THE ANALYSIS OF FIBRE PATH DEFECTS

Dmitry S. Ivanov¹, Julien Volatier, Azhari Rosli, Oliver Nixon-Pearson, Jonathan P.-H. Belnoue, Kevin Potter, Stephen R. Hallett

¹ Advanced Center for Composites Innovation and Science (ACCIS), University of Bristol, UK
Queen's Building, University Walk, Bristol, UK, BS8 1TR
Email: dmitry.ivanov@bristol.ac.uk, web page: www.bristol.ac.uk/composites

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ABSTRACT

The inter-ply properties of prepregs, broadly described by the notions of adhesion, friction sliding, and tack, are critical for the formation of fibre path defects (FPD). Conventional methods of interface testing, such as tack tests, friction pull-out and pull-through tests, can successfully characterize the conditions of stationary ply motion when the scale of relative ply displacement is of an order of 10's of mm. However in reality FPD often occur at much smaller movements of ply (sub-mm scale). This paper discusses a simple experimental technique which can offer the required resolution and, in contrast to the other methods, allows assessing the mode of a defect formation as a function of processing conditions. It was found that a large variety of FPD modes may be observed. The paper also shows that characteristic adhesion values can be derived from optical examination of the defects generated in a controlled fashion.

1 INTRODUCTION

The formation of wrinkles and other fibre path defects (FPD) in prepregs during forming stages is a complicated process, which is governed by many time-dependent and elastic material properties including inter-ply friction, adhesion strength, and bending stiffness of uncured prepreg. The necessary condition for defect occurrence is the generation of an excessive length in one of the plies, i.e. the state when the actual fibre length exceeds the designed ply trajectory. This may occur in the consolidation processes due to the difference between ply-tool and inter-ply friction [1], compaction of thick laminates on curved tool [2, 3], bending of a laminate [4], forming on complex double-curvature tools [5], in-plane bending of a unidirectional tape [6], consolidation of tapered laminate, etc. The excessive length may or may not lead to an FPD, which depends on whether plies can freely slide or inter-ply adhesion impedes the motion. The commonly considered FPD modes include wrinkling (local ply rotation around the axis transverse to the fibre direction), folding (ply rotation around the fibre direction), and in-plane waviness. As will be shown in this paper, there exist other deformation modes.

Various experimental methods are available to characterize the ply interfaces (pull-out, pull-through tests [7], tack tests, etc). These methods provide valuable insight on the material behaviour but this is still debatable whether the test output can be directly used in defect modelling. The major issues are (a) *insufficient resolution*: the material parameters are measured at the displacement of an order of 10's of mm whereas the excessive length is of a sub-mm scale, (b) *artificial conditions*: the conventional tests do not reveal the variety of deformation modes seen in reality (plies in friction tests cannot delaminate, the tack tests eliminate sliding, none of these tests reproduce buckling, in-plane waviness, etc).

The current paper suggests a new experimental program designed to generate characteristic defects in controlled fashion. Two aims are pursued: (1) to study the deformation modes in different materials, and (2) to derive interface properties. To create an excessive length pre-stretching of one of the plies is used. The plies can then reveal the most favourable interaction mechanism upon unloading. The interaction of non-stretched and stretched plies results in the local movement of plies and, as a result, wrinkling, folding, buckling, or sliding. The methods provides data for numerical simulations of the

ply properties. Two toughened interleaved and non-interleaved prepreg systems were investigated to understand the effect of thermoplastic interleaf on the probability of defect occurrence.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The tests were conducted on two toughened prepreg systems developed by Hexcel® and used for aerospace applications: IM7/8552 (where thermoplastic particles are dispersed within plies, nominal thickness 0.13 mm, areal density 206 g/m²) and IMA/M21 (with a distinct interleaf between the plies containing both the thermoplastic particles and a thermosetting resin, nominal thickness 0.18 mm, areal density 194 g/m²). These materials represent different generations of prepreps and were extensively studied and characterised previously [8, 9].

The tests are implemented in several steps (Figure 1): (1) a UD ply (substrate) is stretched along the fibre direction, (2) new plies (superstrate) are laid up on the surface of the substrate ply under tension (symmetrically with respect to the substrate mid-plane), (3) the obtained laminate is vacuum bagged to ensure that the plies are engaged in a contact, (4) vacuum pressure is released, (5) the tensile load is released, (6) the sample is cured in an oven with no applied pressure. The release of the tensile load leads to the contraction of substrate forcing the unloaded superstrate to adopt the excessive length in an energetically favourable deformation mode. The samples are then examined using 3D optical surface measurements and microscopy.

The bulk of the experimental programme was conducted at room temperature. The non-interleaved samples were also tested at elevated temperatures (in the range of 30-90°C).

Figure 1. Sequence of steps to generate an excessive length in the laminate: (1) substrate UD, (2) stretching of the substrate, (3) laminating of tensioned substrate with plies of superstrate (non-symmetrical configuration is shown on the scheme), (4) vacuum pressure is applied and then released, (5) tensile load is released.

The length of substrate plies (800 mm in total) was chosen to maximise the excessive length without exceeding the strain to failure. In all the conducted tests strain in fibres did not exceed 1%. To achieve a better gripping 6 plies of glass-woven 8552 with nominal thickness of 0.35 were attached to form end-tabs (two internal plies with 60 mm length and four external plies with 50 mm length at each side). The end tabs were cured in the hot press at 180°C and 6 bar pressure for 2 hours (the work area of the sample was kept outside of the heated region). The 350 mm long and 60 mm wide superstrate plies were applied along (for wrinkles) or across (for folds) the fibre direction of the substrate. In further notations the laminate will be coded as $[\theta_n, 0^s, \theta_n]$ where 0^s is the substrate ply and θ_n stand for n plies of superstrate oriented at an angle θ to the loading direction. Visible marks on a substrate ply where superstrate plies ended was drawn to observe and measure sliding. The plies were cut from feedstock using an automated ply cutter B&W Genesis 2100.

An Instron with 100 kN load cell was used to stretch the substrate plies at the rate of 1mm/min up to 5-6 kN (interleaved and non-interleaved prepreps) and 9-10 kN (for interleaved prepreps). Vacuum was held for 15 minutes before the load was released at the same rate as was used for loading. At least three samples of each sample configuration/load level were tested. The tests at elevated temperatures were conducted using a similar scheme. After the bagging material the bagged laminate was left in a temperature chamber for 15 min for concurrent processes of debulking and heating.

Dantec Dynamics Q-400 stereo digital image correlation system with two 16 megapixel cameras was used to quantify wrinkle dimensions. The surfaces of cured samples were speckled creating a stochastic pattern of black points on white background. The field view, set approximately as 200 mm by 100 mm, covered most of the FPDs seen on the sample surface. Both front and back surfaces were examined.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Taxonomy of observed defects

The tests revealed a large variety of FPD modes dictated by the material system, laminate configuration, test temperature and applied load. Expected wrinkles and folds occur concurrently or together with laminate buckling, shear deformation of ply interleaf, edge delamination, and elevated roughness. A summary of all the defects is given in Table 1.

Feature/Defect type	Description	Feature/Defect type	Description
<p>Out-of plane wrinkling. Observed in 0° plies of [0°/0°_s/0°] configuration at temperatures 20-70°C both in IMA/M21 (lower density of FPD at higher load) and IM7/8552 prepregs (higher density of FPD at lower load)</p>	<p>Surface texture of ply with folds and splits (full width is shown, load is in vertical direction)</p>		
<p>Macro-buckling Observed in IM7/8552 [90°/0°_s/90°] laminate configuration at room temperature and small loads (higher loads tend to eliminate macro buckling and promote generation of multiple folds)</p>	<p>Surface texture of sample with in-plane waviness: quarter width is shown on, load is in the vertical direction fibre paths are highlighted.</p>		
<p>Shear of the interface and edge or central delamination Observed in both prepregs systems but more pronounced in the non-interleaved IM7/8552.</p>	<p>a) </p>		

<p>Elevated roughness and micro-delaminations</p> <p>Observed in 90° plies [90°₄/0°_s/90°₄] configuration of IM7/8552 at room temperature</p>	
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Table 1. Taxonomy of defects observed in the experiments

The key observation can be summarised as follows:

1. Wrinkles occurred within isolated bands of 5-10 mm wide. They formed due to the decohesion of substrate and superstrate plies followed by the buckling of superstrate (micrography shows that substrate remains straight – Figure 2). Wrinkles were randomly distributed over the sample surface but formed localized bands when their density was high. In average 4-6 wrinkles of similar dimensions along the path of a single fibre could be observed. Hence, it can be suggested that a higher excessive length is accommodated by an increased number of defects rather than by an evolution of defect dimensions.

Figure 2. Cross-section of fold in formed in 90° plies of [90°₂/0°_s/90°₂] laminate.

2. The mechanisms of fold formation was similar. However fold dimensions were much smaller due to lower buckling stiffness in the transverse direction. Folds tended to initiate at the sample edges and either spanned across the entire sample width or propagated through a significant portions of it forming triangular openings. Localised folds led to ply splits. A thicker superstrate tended to cause a reduction of fold amplitude and decohesion length but increase the amount of micro-defects, which displays itself as an elevated roughness of outer plies.
3. None of the tests revealed any significant degree of sliding even at elevated temperatures. Instead it was observed, that at temperatures exceeding 70-80°C, wrinkles were substituted by a pronounced in-plane waviness of superstrate plies (NB: only IM7/8552 was tested at elevated temperatures). In the temperature range of 20-70°C the decohesion length of each wrinkle tended to increase. A certain degree of in-plane waviness was also seen at low temperatures.

Interleaved and non-interleaved system showed very different patterns of behaviour:

1. In [0°₀,0°_s,0°] configuration IM7/8552 loaded to 5-6 kN tend to produce a substantial amount of wrinkles (in excess of 40 per samples) whereas the IMA/M21 at the same load exhibited no wrinkles or other obvious fibre path defects at all. The only noticeable indication of deformation mechanisms was the edge delamination seen at the location where the superstrate plies were terminated. It was assumed that at this load level the excessive length could be accommodated through shearing of thermoplastic interleaves. Increasing the load to 10 kN led to occurrence of wrinkles in the interleaved system. However, the amount of wrinkles was significantly lower and their amplitude is smaller compared to the wrinkles generated in non-interleaved system at lower load.
2. In [90°₀,0°_s,90°] configuration IM7/8552 loaded to below 4 kN produced a macro-buckling mode with no individual folds or splits. Higher loads resulted in the elimination of buckling and the occurrence of localised splits. The interleaved IMA/M21 system did not show any indication of micro or macro defects even when loaded to 9.5kN.

The summary of observed defects and features is given in Table 2.

Material	Lay-up	No. samples	Load, kN	ΔL_{max} , mm	No. wrinkles per side or presence of folds	Edge delamination	In plane waviness
IM7/8552	[0°,0° _s ,0°]	5	5.0-6.1	3.8-4.6	>40	yes	yes
IMA/ M21	[0°,0° _s ,0°]	3	4.9-5.1	3.0-3.3	not present	yes	no
IMA/ M21	[0°,0° _s ,0°]	3	9.2	5.0-5.2	10-20	yes	yes
IM7/8552	[90°,0° _s ,90°]	5	5.0-6.5	3.3-4.5	present	no	no
IMA/ M21	[90°,0° _s ,90°]	3	4.9-5.1	2.5-2.9	not present	no	no
IMA/ M21	[90°,0° _s ,90°]	3	9.0-9.5	5.1-5.2	not present	yes	no

Table 2. Classification of FPD observed in the cured laminates.

3.2 FPD dimensions

Optical strain measurements were used to assess the geometrical characteristics of wrinkles. Two representative samples of [0°,0°_s,0°] configuration were selected: (1) IM7/8552 (loaded to 6.6 kN) and IMA/M21 (loaded to 9.4 kN). Both the front and back surfaces of the samples were characterised. DIC produced a surface profile of the central area of the samples which covered most of generated wrinkles – Figure 3. The majority of out-of-plane wrinkles were observed away from the edges. However, the wrinkles with the highest amplitude were often seen at the edges. Since the obtained samples were not ideally flat a certain criteria had to be applied in regards to what could be considered a wrinkle. Only those wrinkles with the amplitude explicitly above the measurement noise were considered. This corresponded to an empirical threshold on wrinkle amplitude of 0.2 mm.

Figure 3. Map of out-of plane coordinates of points on the surface of a wrinkled sample

The dimensions of every characteristic defect were examined along a line drawn along the fibre/stretching direction. The obtained distributions are shown in Figure 4 and the statistical descriptors of the obtained data are summarized in

Table 3.

Figure 4. a) Distribution of the geometrical parameters of wrinkles, b) Variety of wrinkles in two material systems (the experimental curves are approximated by function (1)).

Test No.	Load (kN)	No. of wrinkle	Amplitude, A (mm)			Decohesion length, L (mm)		
			Highest	Mean	Std.dev	Highest	Mean	Std.Dev
IM7/8552 Front	6.61	19	1.40	0.80	0.39	13.70	10.63	0.99
IM7/8552 Back		22	1.93	0.75	0.57	16.92	11.23	1.76
IMA/M21 Front	9.40	15	0.95	0.44	0.26	15.55	11.80	1.74
IMA/M21 Back		10	1.48	0.43	0.73	17.08	11.10	3.63

Table 3. Measurements of FPD in $[0^\circ, 0^\circ, 0^\circ]$ laminates.

The extreme values of amplitudes and decohesion lengths were far from the mean values however for most wrinkles the geometrical parameters were concentrated within a relatively narrow range around the mean value. Different distributions of amplitudes were observed for the two material. In average non-interleaved system exhibited roughly twice higher values than interleaved prepreg. However, the mean decohesion lengths were very close for both the systems.

3.3 Mechanical properties of the prepreg systems

The dimensions of wrinkles can be related to the material properties (bending stiffness, specific energy of adhesion) and loading conditions. To establish the link, the bent shape of a wrinkle is first approximated. It can be conveniently described by the hyperbolic secant function, which accepts two

parameters as an input. These are amplitude A (distance from yarn mid-plane to the highest point of a wrinkle) and the shape parameter B :

$$w = A \operatorname{sech}(Bx) \quad (1)$$

The shape parameter can be directly related to the decohesion length. In a first approximation it is reasonable to choose $B = 8/L$ as it provides a close match to the observed wrinkle shape. The advantage of the approximation (1) is that it closely reproduces the actual wrinkle shape with two parameters and (2) it naturally satisfies the equilibrium equation of the elastic plate theory dictating the force balance in the partly delaminated superstrate:

$$D \frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} + N \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where N – is the in-plane force transmitted to superstrate from substrate through the shear at the interface in the non-delaminated region, D – is the bending stiffness of the superstrate. Substituting (1) to (2) allows connecting the applied load, the decohesion length, and the bending stiffness:

$$D = N/B^2 \quad (3)$$

From this relation the bending stiffness of a superstrate ply can be derived. It shows that the bending stiffness of the interleaved system is approximately 40% higher compared to the non-interleaved system. The excess length can also be expressed as a function of the geometrical parameters:

$$\Delta = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 dx = \frac{1}{3} A^2 B \quad (4)$$

The elastic energy associated with the buckling of individual wrinkle is now a function of the applied load and the excess length:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} D \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx = \frac{7}{15} D A^2 B^3 = \frac{7}{5} N \Delta \quad (5)$$

In the absence of other deformation mechanisms the total energy associated with the wrinkle formation is presented as the sum of work done on substrate stretching, the energy of ply delamination, and the energy of ply buckling (wrinkle formation). It is reasonable to assume that the substrate stretching is elastic and its energy is fully recovered upon unloading. If the other energy contributions such as the viscous and heat dissipation are neglected, then the specific energy required to delaminate the plies γ can be expressed from the balance of the remaining terms as:

$$\gamma = \frac{14}{5} \frac{N \Delta}{bL} \quad (5)$$

where b is the wrinkle width (presuming that not a single fibre remains unbuckled, b can be chosen to be the sample width).

Table 4 shows the characteristic of the characteristics of the prepregs that were derived for both the systems: IM7/8552 and IMA/M21. The specific energy of decohesion appears to be high – it is comparable to the energy release values of a cured laminate. However, no direct comparison that can be made between the fracture energy and decohesion energy. In the latter case, a considerable fraction of that energy may be released through viscous dissipation. The energy balance also does not take into account the deformation of interleaf, which is believed to play essential role in adopting the excessive length. Thus, the estimate refers to an apparent response of the interleaved material rather than actual

decohesion of interleaf and prepreg. This is suitable for finite element modelling of the process though as would be extremely difficult to model interleaf explicitly.

	IM7/8552	IMA/M21
Bending stiffness D, (Nm ²)	0.012	0.019
Excessive length of an average wrinkle, (mm)	0.15	0.04
Specific energy of decohesion, N/mm	4.2	1.5

Table 4 Mechanical characteristics of IM7/8552 and IMA/M21 derived from the analysis of wrinkle dimensions

5 CONCLUSIONS

The discussed experimental approach revealed a good potential as an instrument for assessing defect formation mechanisms and studying behaviour of prepregs related to small inter-ply movement. The method provides a high resolution measurements and naturally delivers a representative statistics over the variation in local prepreg properties. Most importantly, the approach allows revealing energetically favourable deformation mechanisms.

A much wider range of deformation modes was observed in reality than considered previously. Interestingly, one of the most common deformation mechanisms – inter-ply sliding was not seen in any of the conducted experiments which gives a very different perspective on understanding FPD formation. It appears that for the implemented test set-up the wrinkle formation mechanisms is largely dominated by such factors as the adhesion strength, the bending stiffness of plies, viscosity and shear stiffness of interleaf. At high temperatures the wrinkling is substituted by the formation of in-plane buckles with no indication of sliding.

Two different but not completely dissimilar materials were tested. It was found that the interleaves are fundamentally important in prepreg deformation mechanisms. It was concluded that the interleaf may adopt a considerable fraction of the excessive length through shearing. A higher load is then required to delaminate and buckle a ply. The amplitude and quantity of wrinkles in non-interleaved system were considerably higher though the sample considered merely 40-50% less load applied to the substrate.

The decohesion and stiffness properties of a prepreg can be directly derived from the sample observations. Even though these values are indicative they provide an insight on what characteristic values can be used in the modelling of wrinkling. The interface properties can now complement a new 3D hyper-visco-elastic model for bulk behaviour of toughened prepregs [10] that can confidently predict the generation of the excessive length associated with the non-uniform compaction.

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